

An analysis of State wise monthly electricity generation scenario from renewable sources pre and post Covid-19

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Abstract: Advancing toward the twenty-first century, power is a vital necessity. For humans in the twenty-first century, energy is as essential as food and water. However, as the human population has grown and the need for energy in our life has increased, humans have discovered a variety of additional ways to generate power. Under the rigorous lockdown, which began on March 25, 2020, power consumption from hospitals, critical services, and the residential sector increased, but industrial demand and commercial activity decreased significantly. Total electricity demand in India had not recovered to pre-Covid-19 levels by the end of August 2020. In this paper study the growth pattern of renewable energy sources combination for electricity generation. In methodology section use compound annual growth rate (CAGR), descriptive analysis and pia chat etc. Panel data are obtained from central electricity authority (CEA) of solar, wind, small hydro, biogas, biomass, and other sources from Jan 2019 to Jun 2023. Expected outcomes are performance of solar and wind for electricity generation is very significant compared to other renewable sources. The transition to renewable energy sources is a critical step towards achieving sustainability and energy security. State governments, in collaboration with central agencies, continue to navigate challenges and seize opportunities to foster a resilient and diversified renewable energy sector across the country.

Index Terms – Renewable Energy, Total Final Energy Consumption, Compound Annual Growth Rate.

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth and energy consumption can also be viewed from a policy perspective, as a positive relationship between prices and growth could indicate that energy efficiency policies might slow down economic growth. Furthermore, improving growth policies, particularly in nations with limited renewable energy sources, may have major environmental and social effects. Complicate environmental saving efforts.[1]. Both the population and the need for energy sources are expanding. Different amounts of energy are required around the planet. Compared to developing nations, wealthy nations use more energy. Renewable energy sources are currently the focus of the most concern among people since they are pollution-free, conveniently available, less expensive, and existing in higher amounts on Earth. In order to use renewable energy technology, we must use natural energy sources, such as solar, wind, tidal, biomass, geothermal, etc. These energy sources are inherently green.[2]. To achieve universal access to inexpensive, dependable, sustainable, and modern energy, renewable energy must be deployed more quickly in the fields of power, heat, and transportation. But if the pace doesn't pick up, the proportion of renewable energy in total final energy consumption (TFEC) will continue to be low. Only somewhat higher than the 16 percent from a decade earlier, the share of renewable energy in TFEC in 2020 was only 19.1 percent[3]. The Indian government understands the numerous benefits that electrification provides to households, as well as the limits that people without access to reliable electricity services face. Without power, homes are impoverished, social services are poorly delivered, and women and girls have less chances. Over the previous decade, the government has increased the emphasis of national policy on power access, and this commitment has been backed up with large resources. India's national policy ambition of universal electricity coverage is also congruent with the UN's Sustainable Energy for All initiative, which aims for full access to modern energy services by 2030.[4]. The Indian government is also providing several

financial incentives to promote renewable energy, such as subsidies for solar and wind power projects. The government is also developing a green energy corridor to transmit renewable energy from remote areas to major population centers.

The transition to renewable energy is essential for India's sustainable development. Renewable energy can help India to improve its energy security, reduce its carbon emissions, improve air quality, create jobs, and promote rural development.

II. Review of literature.

Pillai & Banerjee (2009) indicates that various renewable energy initiatives, such as solar water heaters, wind turbines, and photovoltaics, are growing quickly. Wind and solar energy will be used to reach the anticipated MNRE goal. However, measures for small hydro need to be accelerated. Renewable energy growth is now being fueled by grants and subsidies.

Sisodia & Singh (2016) say that compared to affluent nations, academic research on renewable energy in India has a limited scope. However, a significant change occurs in the government of India's research and development push for renewable energy after 2008. Kumar & Rawat (2019) analyze the development and growth of renewable energy in India as well as the simultaneous requirement for a hybrid renewable energy model for India's electrification of rural areas.

Carfora et al. (2019) Findings are Granger causality test for India and Indonesia is not significant for both countries of energy consumption, income, and price.

Doso et al., (2020) Findings involvement of society and researcher/ scientist may proper utilization of small hydro power for future energy security.

Akter & Bagchi (2021) Finding show that solar energy is a key factor in India's rural areas in reducing energy poverty. Access to solar energy for disadvantaged social groups is improved by providing subsidized or free solar energy.

Ghosh et al. (2021) finding is proper use of agricultural waste to generate revenue as well as future energy security. They also find decentralization of waste collection centers attracts more people to waste utilization.

Kaur et al. (2022) Biogas potential is 265,542 million m³ to help the strength the biogas plants for distribution of Indian power sector.

III. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data Source

The main source for data on renewable energy in India is the Central Electricity Authority (CEA), which also provides data at the state, regional, and national levels. From April 2016 to June 2023, we used monthly data broken down by state. Wind, solar, biomass, biogas, small hydro, and other sources (municipal garbage) are also included.

3.2 Methodology

When calculating the average growth rate for a given time in the methodology section, we utilise the compound annual growth rate (CAGR). When profits are assumed to be reinvested at the end of each year, CAGR is a measurement of the average annual growth rate of an investment over a given period.

$$CAGR = \left(\frac{FV}{PV} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

FV= Future value

PV= Present value

n= Number of years

For graphical analysis The CAGR growth pattern is illustrated using MS Excel, and the primary and secondary axes of the pivot graph are used to depict the units and percentage values of the sources for all the Indian states in the year 2022.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Wind Energy

The domestic wind power industry in India is the industry leader and has made steady progress. The growth of the wind sector has produced a robust ecosystem, project operating skills, and an annual production base of over 12,000 MW. With a total installed capacity of 40.08 GW (as of December 31, 2021), the nation now has the fourth-highest wind capacity in the world, with 1.46 GW built between January and December 2021. 68.08 billion units were produced by wind energy projects between January and December of 2021[12].

Source: Centre Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

Figure 1 illustrates that the compound annual growth rate for producing electricity from wind between April 2016 and June 2023 is (-1.9%) each month. From 2231.34 MU in April 2016 to 11557.77 MU in June 2023, the total amount of electricity produced by wind increased at an average rate of -1.9% each month. The generation increased when the wind direction shifted. June, July, August, and September account for over 74% of the world's wind energy production. The major wind energy firms in the nation have all been impacted.

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

An important natural resource for the generation of power in India is wind energy. Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Telangana, and Kerala are among the coastal states that produce wind energy, as shown in Figure 1.a. In these states, wind energy will account for about 95% of the total energy generated in India in 2022.

4.2 Solar Energy

India has set the ambitious objective of generating 40 GW of rooftop solar capacity by 2022. However, rooftop PV development has been low, with just about 3 GW of capacity deployed since 2015, compared to 30 GW for solar. This is due, in part, to the difficulty of reconciling several commercial incentives under the present regulation policy: A vast percentage of residential consumers pay low, subsidized power tariffs, decreasing or, in certain instances, removing the savings attainable from self-consumption.[13].

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

According to the graph, solar power generation has a CAGR of (-2.6%), meaning that the quantity of monthly growth in electricity production is increasing at a declining rate of (-2.6%). In absolute terms, energy will be produced in the range of 1041.27 MU to 9607.58 MU from April 2016 to June 2023. The good news is that solar energy has a big potential in India. There are typically 300 sunny days per year, and the IEA anticipates "explosive growth" for solar energy there, not least because by 2030, solar energy will be less expensive than coal-fired power, even with associated storage cost of batteries.

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

In terms of producing solar energy, India comes in third in Asia and fourth overall. India's National Solar Mission was started in 2010. By the end of 2020, 20GW was to be developed. However, this has already been done as there has been a lot of activity in this area since then. Figure 2.a shows that Rajasthan is the state that generates the most solar electricity, followed by Karnataka, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Kerala, and Orissa. 95% of the world's solar electricity will be produced in these states in 2022. As a result, we say that the southern, middle, and western parts of the north mostly use solar energy.

4.3 Biomass Energy

Plants produce organic material known as biomass (both terrestrial and aquatic and their derivatives), which is a product of natural resources such as land, water, air, and solar energy and has enormous potential as a non-conventional or renewable source of energy.[7].

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

The graph above demonstrates that the biomass electricity generation CAGR value is 0.3%, which indicates that the rate of increase for electricity generation month over month is rising albeit at a relatively slow pace. If the systems are constructed appropriately, it is possible to use biomass energy systems as a component of an energy source that is both environmentally responsible and fosters long-term development. In order to give any significant energy to development in the existing environment, biomass output must expand. Biomass is an additional inexpensive and ecologically friendly energy source.[10].

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

Figure 3.a above shows that 90% of the biomass used to generate power comes from Punjab, Rajasthan, Haryana, and Maharashtra, with the remaining 10% coming from the other 32 states. One third of the biomass used to generate energy from biomass comes from Chhattisgarh. Regulators and policymakers are becoming more interested in electricity based on biomass as the country transitions to carbon-free power generation.

4.4 Biogas Energy

Biogas is a gas that is a further mixture of methane, carbon dioxide, and a little amount of hydrogen sulphur dioxide that is produced through the decomposition of biomass base materials include crop waste, cattle manure, municipal and sewage waste, food waste, and so on. As a byproduct, the digested slurry is converted into organic rich manure for use in farming. Given the 536.76 million cattle, the livestock excrement from these biomass materials has the greatest potential for the construction of biogas facilities[11].

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

The previous fig. 4, which displays a monthly CAGR of 1.9% for electricity production from biogas, predicts that energy growth will be 1.9% the following month. Between April 2016 and May 2023, the nation's power production from biogas rises from 853.93 MU to 1000.32 MU in absolute terms. Its annual production varies depending on trash generation, with the majority of it occurring from November to April.

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

Utilising biogas is a highly efficient approach to produce electricity from a sustainable energy source. This is only true, however, if it is feasible to responsibly and cheaply exploit the heat that the power generator creates. Figure 4.a demonstrates that Maharashtra, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, and Tamil Nadu produce 90% of the world's biogas electricity. In order for India to use biogas for electricity in 2022, these four states have contributed. 33 other states in India do not contribute more than 5%.

4.5 Small Hydro

Small hydropower is often "run-of-river," which means that any dams or barrages are typically only weirs and that little to no water is typically stored. The only purpose of the civil works is to control the water level at the hydro-plant's intake. As a result, run-of-river installations do not have the same negative environmental effects as huge hydro[14].

In figure 5 shows a CAGR of (-0.4%) for small hydropower's growth rate in producing energy. Another method of boosting electricity production from tiny hydro from April 2016 to June 2023 is to use a negative figure to illustrate that the rate of growth is falling from month to month.

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

Between the months of April 2016 and June 2023, it increases in absolute terms from 757.44 MU to 966.22 MU. Building sustainable SHP plants in India will be a labor-intensive process. First, India has a very different grasp of environmental challenges than western countries have, as well as a very different attitude towards environmental sustainability. These challenges aren't given much consideration at the policy level or on an individual basis.[15].

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

We can observe from Fig. 5.a that the states closest to rivers—Himanchal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Punjab, Orissa, J&K, and Andhra Pradesh—provide the majority of the electricity produced by small hydroelectric plants. In India, these states will provide 80% of the country's small hydroelectricity in 2022. R K Singh stated in the Rajya Sabha on February 7, 2023 that the average hydroelectricity generation across all states is 4.94 GW.

Source: Central Electricity Authority, Estimated by Author

In the given fig.6, we can clearly see that the wind share is going to decline and share of solar is going to increase from 2016 to 2023. In 2016, the wind share was highest among other renewable energy sources, but it went down and now, its share has come down to 33.20 percent. On the other hand, solar which was second in share of renewable energy in 2016. Now it is contributing highest and more than 50% share in renewable energy in India. The reason for this increment in the share of solar energy is that government policy is more emphasizing in the production of solar energy. Some of the project and scheme like Solar parks, ultra-mega solar power projects, grid-connected solar rooftop initiatives, and the Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha Evam Utthaan Mahabhiyaan (PM KUSUM) are all increasing the percentage of solar energy. In the automobile sector government is also giving subsidies to promote the solar vehicles in India. Some of these policies are the reason for the increment of the solar share in the renewable energy. Other energy sources like biomass, biogas and small hydro contribution are low as compared to these two sources giants which are contributing more than 80% of the share in renewable energy sources in India. Finally, we say that after COVID-19 solar energy share on renewable energy generation increased compared to other sources i.e. wind, biomass, biogas and others.

V. Conclusion

India's domestic wind power industry is a global leader, with a robust ecosystem and advanced project operating skills. With an annual production base exceeding 12,000 MW, India contributes significantly to renewable energy targets. The industry's total installed capacity demonstrates India's commitment to sustainability, bringing economic and environmental benefits and solidifying its position in the global renewable energy scene. The goal of GOI to 40 GW of rooftop solar by 2022 faces challenges like lack of awareness, complex regulations, financing limitations, and technical issues. The steady but minimal growth in biomass electricity generation, with a CAGR of 0.3%. Despite this, there is potential for biomass energy systems as a valuable energy source, and further research could enhance its contribution to sustainable and renewable energy. Biogas, a mixture of methane, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen sulphur dioxide, is produced from biomass materials like crop waste, livestock manure, and food waste, with the 536.76 million cattle population having the most potential. India's commitment to its renewable energy goals, as outlined in its National Solar Mission, National Wind Mission, and other initiatives, reflects a long-term vision for sustainable energy development. As the country continues to expand its renewable energy capacity and invest in grid infrastructure and storage solutions, it moves closer to achieving a more reliable, secure, and sustainable energy future. In this journey towards a cleaner and more resilient energy sector, India's experience with the mixture of solar, wind, biomass, biogas, and small hydro serves as an instructive model for other nations seeking to balance the benefits of renewable energy with the challenges of fluctuating generation. It highlights the need for flexible grid systems, innovative technologies, and policy frameworks that encourage a harmonious coexistence of renewable and conventional energy sources while addressing environmental concerns and energy security imperatives.

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